

Disaggregated and Transparent Multi-band Optical Continuum across Access, Horseshoe Aggregation, and Metro IPoWDM Networks (Invited)

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The limitations of segmented and power-inefficient legacy optical networks underscore the need for a disaggregated, transparent multi-band optical continuum spanning access, aggregation, and metro domains.

In this work we demonstrate the first field trial of a disaggregated and transparent multi-band optical network interconnecting access, aggregation, and metro segments over both C and O-bands. The proposed architecture extends the optical continuum from antenna sites through O-band access links to aggregation hubs, and further into a C-band metro-core network, eliminating intermediate opto-electronic conversions. The data plane integrates SOA-based O-band switching for dynamic signal routing and loss compensation, while the control plane is realized through an innovative hierarchical SDN-based solution. This control plane orchestrates end-to-end transparent paths across multiple domains, spectral bands, and layers, leveraging standardized protocols and models for interoperability. Experimental validation shows the seamless multi-band interconnection, demonstrating effective multi-domain orchestration, optical transparency, and control scalability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-band optical networks enable simultaneous achievement of higher capacity and enhanced node connectivity [1–6]. Concurrently, the advent of IPoWDM technologies leveraging coherent pluggable transceivers is accelerating the convergence of

IP and photonic layers [7]. Several valuable studies have highlighted the advantages of transparent inter-domain traversal, supported by specialized analytical tools for end-to-end estimation of non-linear physical impairments, including those arising from multi-band operation [3]. Notably, transparent multi-band

interconnection between network segments offers the potential to minimize costly and power-intensive opto-electronic conversions [8]. Nevertheless, a comprehensive validation that incorporates both multi-band data and control planes has not yet been demonstrated. For instance, the study in [9] integrates control and data planes, but is restricted to C-band operation only.

In this paper, we propose, implement, and validate the first field trial of a multi-band disaggregated optical network that transparently interconnects cell-site access in the O-band, an aggregation horseshoe utilizing both C and O-bands, and a C-band metro-core network. The O-band extends transparently from the local exchange in the access domain to antenna sites, enabling front-haul connectivity to one of the aggregation hubs. Meanwhile, the C-band spans transparently from aggregation to the metro layer, eliminating the need for electronic regeneration.

This paper is an extended version of the conference paper [10]. The following novel contributions have been included: (i) previous work analysis reported in Sec. 2, (ii) access-aggregation-metro architecture supporting optical continuum, detailed in the completely new Sec. 3, (iii) significantly expanded Control Plane section, including new contributions (see Sec. 4, (iv) new results in data plane measurements and experimental assessment as reported in Sec. 5 and 6 (See for example the newly generated figures 11, 15, 16, and 13.

2. PREVIOUS WORKS

This paper introduces a novel and comprehensive network architecture, incorporating specific innovations in each enabling technology. This section reviews the state of the art in both network architecture and enabling technologies.

Access-Aggregation network architecture. Recent advancements in Access-Aggregation optical network architectures have focused on enhancing flexibility and energy efficiency to meet the growing demands of next-generation communication systems.

In [11], a novel approach utilizing light-tree structures and point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers has been proposed to greatly enhance multiplexing gains while considering the operational costs tied to network expansions and upgrades. In [12], strategies for deploying energy-efficient Distributed Unit (DU) and Centralized Unit (CU) configurations, along with optimized lightpath provisioning, have been explored to support service-oriented 5G metro access and aggregation networks. In [13], the development of reconfigurable optical crosshaul architectures has been investigated to support 6G radio access networks. Such architectures aim to provide dynamic bandwidth allocation and improved network adaptability to varying traffic demands. In [14], disaggregation and cloudification of metropolitan area networks is investigated in terms of enabling technologies and impact on architecture, cost, and power consumption.

All the aforementioned valuable works that address the evolution of access-aggregation optical network architectures do not focus on a comprehensive architecture providing disaggregated and transparent multi-band optical continuum across access, horseshoe aggregation, and metro IPoWDM networks.

IP over WDM (IPoWDM) The advancement of IPoWDM technology has recently gained momentum, largely due to the emergence of high-speed coherent transceivers with compact designs, such as the Quad Small Form-Factor Pluggable Double Density (QSFP-DD). Techno-economic analyses of IPoWDM infrastructures have been conducted in previous studies [15], which also include evaluations of power consumption [16]. From a control plane standpoint, the Telecom Infra Project (TIP) has explored

strategies to tackle the challenges associated with multi-layer environments. Specifically, the MANTRA whitepaper [17] presents two SDN-based management approaches for IPoWDM devices: (i) the Dual Southbound Interface (SBI) model, where both the IP and optical SDN controllers interface with the device, but only the IP SDN controller has write privileges; and (ii) the Single SBI model, in which the IP SDN controller is solely responsible for configuring the device. Both methodologies rely on a hierarchical SDN controller to oversee multi-domain operations while delegating certain control functions to lower-level controllers. These solutions have been implemented and analyzed in prior works [18–21].

SDN Control of optical networks. Software Define Networking (SDN) is a control model based on several distinct properties: logically centralized control, control and data plane formal separation and the adoption of a set of best practices such as model-driven development, enabling a steady softwareization of the network. Relying on well-proven and mature protocols such as NETCONF, RESTCONF or gNMI and the use of the Yang modeling language [22]), the evolution of SDN for optical networks is driven by new use cases and scenarios, including the controllability of new devices and systems (e.g. [23]), their role in new 5G and beyond services [24] or the decomposition of functional aspects such as dedicated path computation elements [25].

SOA-based switching solutions. Semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOAs) have been widely explored as key components in optical metro-access networks due to their ability to provide loss compensation, signal regeneration, and dynamic switching [26]. It has been demonstrated to be a feasible solution for multiband operation to support Xhaul traffic [27]. Furthermore, it is easy to integrate with passive components to be integrated, e.g., OADM [28].

Multi-domain IPoWDM network orchestration Multi-domain IPoWDM network orchestration involves coordinating and automating operations across various network domains to enable seamless service delivery. This orchestration requires careful management of the available domains and the application of necessary correlations to achieve a comprehensive and unified network. Aligned with this, the authors in [29] demonstrate (exploring a fully emulated multiband data plane) a valid integration of two different optical domains, also including a successful optical path provision in both domains.

Telemetry and automation in optical networks. Optical network automation and failure management require measuring the status and the performance of the different network devices to anticipate any degradation that impact on the QoT. Pervasive network telemetry entails collecting large amounts of measurements from different sources and with very fine granularity. In view of that, the authors in [30] proposed a distributed architecture that takes advantage of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to reduce data dimensionality. In addition to telemetry, optical network automation requires accurate physical layer models, not only for provisioning but also to enable effective monitoring during lightpath operation.

Impairment-aware path computation The open-source project Gaussian Noise in Python (GNPy) is the reference tool for the optical transport modeling of WDM optical transmission networking [9, 31, 32]. GNPy approximates transparent lightpaths as additive white and Gaussian noise channels. The Quality of Transmission (QoT) degradation of each network element (fiber propagation, optical amplifiers, reconfigurable add/drop multiplexers, coherent transceivers) is independently modeled to al-

Fig. 1. Traditional Telco network architecture, including the cell site access, aggregation, and metro segments. O-E-O conversion is performed at each segment border.

Fig. 2. Proposed Access-Aggregation-Metro architecture utilizing both C and O-band. The rigid segregation of network segments is avoided, forming what is called as the optical continuum.

low disaggregated network management. Other relevant works for impairment-aware path computation and optical digital twin include [33–36]. In this work, to account for detrimental physical layer effects on the quality of Multi-Band transmission, we instead adopt the closed-form formalism of [3, 37, 38] because: (i) this formalism takes into account the impact of SRS over a spectrum of 30–35 THz, which is our case here, and (ii) it predicts very accurately the performance of links with a span length shorter than 30 km. The latter is important because aligned with the performed experiments and also because there are links inside the European operator’s network that measure as little as 2 km. The closed-form abstraction models employed herein are based on several approximations detailed in [37]. These approximations are applicable in this context as well. Another notable work in this context is proposed in [34] (i.e., the OCATA network digital twin) that uses AI/ML to extract and exploit in phase and quadrature constellation information to enable deep understanding of the characteristics of lightpaths that can be used for accurate QoT estimation and efficient failure management.

3. ACCESS-AGGREGATION-METRO ARCHITECTURE SUPPORTING OPTICAL CONTINUUM

The architecture shown in Fig. 1 represents the reference traditional Telco network architecture where optical termination and electronic processing is performed at each network segment border. It includes the cell site access, aggregation, and metro segments.

The cell site is the physical location where cellular network equipment is installed to provide 5G wireless coverage. It consists of antennas, radios, and other networking equipment communicating with mobile devices and connecting them to the internet through cell site gateways (i.e., CSGW).

The aggregation network is the infrastructure that interconnects multiple 5G cell sites, transporting their data toward the metro network and ultimately to the core network and the in-

ternet. It typically consists of up to ten sites interconnected in a horseshoe topology. The typical distance between cell sites and aggregation sites is in the range of 5 to 10 km, while the distance between cell sites varies from 5 to 20 km. Each aggregation site includes aggregation routers/switches and optical transport equipment. The horseshoe is terminated at two Hub sites, which also host the computing resources required by the Telecom Operator to serve the considered area (of few squared kilometers) for both broadband and 5G access. Furthermore, the Hub sites provide the interconnection to the metro segment.

The metro infrastructure consists of regional sites including Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (ROADM) for effective WDM high-speed fiber transport. The typical topology is mesh, with typical distance between metro sites in the range of 20 to 80 km.

Traditionally, each segment is operated in the optical C-band only. Furthermore, each segment is electronically terminated at its borders, as highlighted in Fig. 1. That is, the connection to/from a cell site is traditionally terminated in a router at the corresponding aggregation site and, similarly, the connections to/from aggregation sites are terminated at both Hubs.

This traditional Telco network architecture suffers from two main limitations. First, it is not able to cope with the continuous increase of network traffic due to the exhaustion of bandwidth resources within the C-band. Second, it does not provide a sustainable, power-efficient solution, given the optical termination and electronic processing at each segment border.

Fig. 2 illustrates the proposed Access-Aggregation-Metro architecture, designed to overcome the aforementioned limitations. First, it addresses bandwidth constraints by utilizing two optical bands: the C-band and the O-band. Second, it eliminates optical termination and electronic processing at each segment border, allowing for optical bypass of selected services within specific bands. This approach removes the rigid segregation of network segments, forming what is known as the optical continuum. Figs. 3-5 present the schematic internal architecture of each network site.

Fig. 3 shows the architecture at the cell and aggregation sites. The cell site is equipped with IPoWDM nodes and CSGWs that exploit WDM connectivity in the O-band, also leveraging low-cost transceivers designed for the broad data center market. The aggregation site, part of the horseshoe infrastructure, consists of devices that operate in two different bands. The O-band switch is used for the mobile traffic, providing transparent interconnection towards the cell site. The C-band ROADM is used for residential and business services, providing transparent interconnection between aggregation sites. Aggregation sites may also include transponders or IPoWDM nodes to support high-bandwidth connectivity services to the metro/core network. Band separators, also called band splitters/couplers, are used to separate the transmission at C and O-bands. They are low-cost devices widely used in bidirectional single-fiber access networks.

Fig. 4 shows the internal architecture of the aggregation Hub site and how it is interconnected to other aggregation sites. At the horseshoe Hub site, mobile connectivity services are electronically terminated and processed, leveraging locally available edge computing resources. Thus, the O-band switch is a 1-degree type, meaning it is used to aggregate and disaggregate WDM O-band signals. On the other hand, the connectivity provided in the C-band is not always terminated in this site. In fact, selected wavelengths bypass IPoWDM nodes and transparently reach metro locations, implementing the optical continuum con-

cept. Since only the C-band extends to the metro network, band separators are used only towards the aggregation site, where both bands coexist.

Fig. 5, for the sake of completeness, shows the internal architecture of the metro site and how it interconnects with the proposed horseshoe Hub site. In this figure, a traditional architecture is represented, leveraging only C-band connectivity that extends toward multiple directions across multi-degree ROADMs. Alternatively, innovative multi-band technology (using C, L and possibly S and E bands) or space division multiplexing architectures could be adopted [39–41].

Fig. 3. Architecture at the cell and aggregation sites.

Fig. 4. Architecture at the aggregation and Hub sites.

Fig. 5. Architecture at the Hub and metro sites.

4. CONTROL PLANE ARCHITECTURE

To support the proposed optical continuum, several control plane extensions have been designed and implemented. Specifically, Fig. 6 shows the proposed control plane architecture including the following control elements, specifically enhanced

Fig. 6. Overall Control plane architecture.

to manage both intra- and inter-domain IPoWDM connectivity across multiple bands/layers.

The *Per-domain Optical SDN Controller* is based on ONOS, version 3.0.0, whose official distribution provides a solid base to control disaggregated optical networks and can be extended to support reliable hierarchical deployments, as shown in [42]. One controller is deployed in the aggregation domain, and another controller is deployed in the metro segment. In each domain, the controller is devoted to: (i) present an abstraction of the data-plane sub-systems (i.e., devices and links) to the upper control-plane layers (i.e., the network orchestrator can retrieve a detailed description of the network topology); (ii) receive service configuration requests from the upper layers and translate them into a set of configuration messages to data-plane devices, using the appropriate protocols and format for each device.

Specifically, several extensions are applied to the official ONOS distribution to enable the features required in the considered scenario. Among the several extensions, we mention the ones that most affected the controller features and have been contributed to the community.

- The controller core is upgraded to support flex-grid and multi-band operations, e.g., when asking a new intent it is now possible to specify flex-grid optical channels in band O, L, C and S;
- The controller northbound interface is upgraded with a set of REST APIs supporting seamless communication with the TAPI network orchestrator, e.g., it is now possible to export the status of each wavelength channel registered on a link;
- The establishment of lightpaths is now possible specifying ROADMs ports as ingress and/or egress endpoints. This upgrade involved modifications in controller northbound, core, and southbound, and is essential to support the establishment of transparent multi-domain intents.

The *Intra-domain Network Orchestrator* is responsible for interworking with the per-domain Optical SDN controllers and exposes a TAPI compliant (i.e., Transport API [43]) interface towards upper layers components. It is based on CTTC FlexOpt SDN controller, which is an SDN controller framework developed in C++, following a highly modular design, so specific functions such as algorithms, southbound protocols and additional functionality are implemented as shared link libraries that can be configured and loaded on demand. The justification for the deployment of the optical orchestrator is many-fold and includes, notably the following aspects:

First, being able to provision data connectivity services (e.g., spectrum services) across multiple optical domains may require coordinating multiple optical SDN controllers which may have their own - potentially proprietary - exposed North Bound Interface (NBI) [22] and, in this sense, one of the main functional aspects of this network orchestrator is to provide a set of open and standard interfaces (based on a collection of YANG models and the usage of the RESTCONF protocol) to clients, enabling homogeneous control regardless of the underlying optical controller implementation, acting as a proxy server and mediator. In this regard, the TAPI Network Orchestrator software exports multiple services using protocols such as RESTCONF/YANG, PCEP or BGPLS. The key services are Topology Management, Connectivity Service Management and Path Computation, as defined in the TAPI project. TAPI interfaces are based on YANG data models relying on the RESTCONF protocol. Such interfaces and data models have been experimentally extended and enhanced to the specifics of this work, in line with standardization efforts within the TAPI working group. In particular, this include support multi-band networking, which has been modeled and multiple media channel pools for a single Optical Multiplex Session, each with its own frequency range, and to include basic Physical Layer Impairments (PLI) information as previously shown in [25].

Second, the optical orchestrator may perform additional functions such as externalized path computation, providing a set of constraints to the optical SDN Controller, including providing precomputed attributes of the media channel such as the frequency slot and links or QoT validation upon successful provisioning. Specifically, in this deployment, the Intra-domain Network Orchestrator exposes the TAPI set of data models [43].

The TAPI project is charted under the Linux Foundation Open Network Modeling and Interfaces (ONMI) project, and provides technology-agnostic interfaces to functional modules such as topology, connectivity and notification services, including support for technology-specific interface profiles based on the Photonic Media layer (L0-WDM), and includes support for controller based telemetry, as explained in [44].

The approach chosen for this work deploys a dedicated orchestration instance on top of each controller. Although a single orchestration instance could abstract multiple optical controllers, such option requires further work in order to avoid, for example, addressing conflicts and uniform naming. Conversely, with our approach, the optical orchestrator is provisioned with credentials to access the Optical SDN controller and upon successful authentication, retrieves topological information from the per-domain controller using the extended northbound ONOS REST-APIs interface including devices, ports and per-band spectral information. Local identifiers are mapped to TAPI universally unique identifiers (uuids) and, in turn, exports a north bound interface based on standard TAPI data models to the inter-domain, hierarchical controller. The orchestrator is also able to map TAPI requests for media channel connectivity services to the ONOS interface for optical intents, mapping TAPI service interface points to ONOS ports.

The *(Multi-domain) IP SDN Controller* is a python based prototype SDN Controller that provides provides the Multi-domain IPoWDM network orchestration with the means to retrieve the IP information and create IP adjacencies, among other capabilities. The northbound interface is compatible with IETF's RFC 8345 YANG data model, extended with RFC 8346's layer 3 topologies also partially adopting the draft [45] to support OSPF parameters such as metric, area-id or extending BGP sup-

Fig. 7. Detailed control plane architecture in association to the OMB-PCE and optical layer configuration.

Fig. 8. Distributed intelligence, including telemetry and optical network digital twin.

port with parameters such as peer-as or local-as among others, adding transceivers and port speed as part of the interface description. Finally RFC 8944 (i.e, the layer-2 termination point attributes) was extended to support frequency and grid. The southbound interface supports NETCONF and REST interfaces to directly interact with the SONiC devices that may be deployed in different domains.

The *Multi-domain IPoWDM Network Orchestrator* is based on E-lighthouse Network Planner (ENP) software. It interacts with all the Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) of Multi-domain IP SDN Controller and the Intra-domain Network Orchestrator (exploiting TAPI), as well as an external inventory database containing inter-domain links and pluggable-to-ROADM connections. Enhanced to correlate multi-domain optical and IP layers, provides a unified IPoWDM multilayer network view and control. Additionally, the orchestrator initiates requests for a new IP adjacency by soliciting from the optical PLI-aware Multiband Path Computation Element (PCE). Upon receiving a valid path, the orchestrator executes the necessary requests using the NBIs of the connected controllers.

The *PLI-aware Multiband Path Computation Element (OMB-PCE)* is based on an optical multi-band routing engine which ensures that: i) routing is implemented by means of an efficient spectrum and modulation-format assignment; and ii) the impact of physical layer effects over the selected optical paths is esti-

Fig. 9. Aggregation horseshoe in O and C-bands from Hub1 to Hub2, including two access cell sites. In-field metro network in C-band from Hub2. Optical aggregation-metro continuum transparently bypassing IPoWDM at Hub2.

mated and key system parameters are tweaked to attain QoT target values (BER, OSNIR, OSNR, etc). This way, the planning tool ascertains the conditions that maximize the total capacity of the network while it minimizes the global blocking probability and prevents network misconfiguration.

The OMB-PCE is integrated within the considered control plane architecture as shown in Fig. 7. During network initialization, it retrieves a domainless optical infrastructure view from the Multi-domain IPoWDM orchestrator (exploiting TAPI v2.1), then it waits for lightpath requests that the orchestrator submits exploiting TAPI v2.1. Upon request, the OMB-PCE computes the optimal path together with the optimal operation parameters considering the current network status (e.g., spectrum resource availability and all established lightpaths) and replies to the orchestrator.

The OMB-PCE functionality is realized by means of the following consecutive steps:

Network Topology Implementation: the network topology is defined by setting the connectivity pattern between the nodes including nodes, edges and amplifiers, the available optical bands, the capacity per band.

Routing Modulation and Spectral Assignment (RMSA): the operation is completed in two intermediate steps: i) a preliminary spectrum and modulation format assignment (SMA) is made for a number of the k-shortest paths, and ii) the Optical Signal to Noise plus Interference Ratio (OSNIR) for these paths is estimated taking into account the impact of the physical layer effects by means of closed-form expressions. During this phase, the algorithm either selects or rejects a lightpath and the RMSA assignment is completed. A path is rejected if: a) no contiguous spectral slots are available in any optical band to support the end-to-end connection; b) either the OSNIR of the candidate lightpath falls short of the QoT estimator threshold or the OSNIR of at least one of the already established lightpaths would perform below the QoT threshold due to the presence of this candidate lightpath.

In either (a), (b) cases, the rejected lightpath is assigned the next available path from the sorted list of k-shortest paths and it is then re-iterated. If these paths are all rejected, the first step is repeated using a lower cardinality SMA values. If no path is retained, the engine registers a blocking condition. For the derivation of the successful assignments of the lightpaths, the corresponding arrays for each link of the path are updated, e. g., arrays of power, modulation format, consumed frequency slots.

The validity of the physical layer model and effectiveness of

the control-plane integration are confirmed in [37]. Here, we would point out the importance to incorporate to the routing engine a physical layer-aware RMSA based on closed-form expression as this is the only way to attain service provisioning within a time frame compatible to the dynamicity of the events. Moreover, to ensure the scalability, it is crucial to use rapidly converging algorithms to determine the optimization launch power per band or even per channel. This approach can be further expanded towards a more fine-grained power optimization, partitioning each band in smaller segments. Thus, this work uses the method of simulating annealing [46] where the energy function E is given by Eq.(1):

$$E = \sum_{\text{band}} \left(\log \frac{\text{OSNIR}_{\text{band}}}{C_{\text{band}}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where the constants C_{band} and $\text{OSNIR}_{\text{band}}$ allow to tune the target performance per band. In this work, we update the approach of [8] using a low target OSNIR and gradually increase it until no further improvement is possible. Specifically, this method gives better results (e.g. OSNIR flatness across the spectrum of interest) compared to [8].

Distributed intelligence. Finally, a distributed intelligence is used to collect and analyze measurements close to the data sources and uses AI/ML-based transmission models for lightpaths degradation detection and root cause analysis. The architecture is outlined in Fig. 8. A centralized telemetry manager is in charge of receiving, processing, and storing telemetry measurements in a repository (a time-series database). Telemetry agents are deployed as part of the node agents and consist of several components, including algorithms for data processing, e.g., for dimensionality reduction. The centralized OCATA NDT consumes telemetry measurements for training and fine-tuning AI/ML models representing optical transmission through lightpaths. Therefore, it requires access to the network topology and the connections database in the SDN controller. OCATA lightpath models are deployed at the node agents, where algorithms compare local telemetry measurements against the model, so degradations can be rapidly detected and its root cause be localized [47].

5. DATA PLANE INFRASTRUCTURE

Fig. 9 shows the proposed data plane architecture, realistically reproducing next generation Operator's access-metro networks. The *access domain* consists of cell-site nodes connected to a

Fig. 10. Control plane architecture workflow.

horseshoe network including up to ten aggregation nodes (two in the experiment, $Aggr_1$ and $Aggr_2$) with one Hub node at each end (Hub_1 and Hub_2). Aggregation nodes are in the range of 5 to 10 km, serving an area of few kilometers for both broadband and 5G access. Each node operates in two optical bands, C and O. In each direction, each Aggr node includes (i) a pair of passive band splitter/couplers, (ii) a degree-two ROADM with Add/Drop module operating in the C-band and (iii) a prototype of SOA-based ROADM operating in the O-band. The O-band OADM comprises two AWGs with an LWDM grid, two O-band SOAs, two 50:50 splitters for dropping and adding data channels and a microcontroller to control the OADM. The SOAs function as gates and amplifiers for dynamically blocking or passing each channel.

Each Hub node, for what concerns the aggregation segment, includes one band splitter/coupler and a degree-one ROADM in each band. Hub nodes also represent the entry point of the metro network, i.e., they include elements controlled by either the Agrr or the Metro SDN Controller. The *metro domain* consists of a mesh network, where links are few tens of km long and nodes consist of multi-degree ROADMs in C-band only. In this experiment, the metro segment is in the field, including a metro-regional link of 80 km of fiber in the Turin area. Transmission systems in the C-band include 100/200 Gb/s transponders and IPoWDM switches equipped with SONiC operating system and 400ZR(+) transceivers. In the O-band, LWDM 25G transceivers are adopted in Layer3 switches.

Traditionally, access and metro systems are managed as separate domains from both data and control plane perspective, with inefficient electronic termination at Hub central offices. In this work, optical bypass of the IPoWDM box at Hub2 is implemented for a C-band channel, which transparently reaches remote metro sites. This way, the O-band serves traffic confined within the access and aggregation segments, while the C-band can also be used for high-speed connections transparently crossing the boundary between aggregation and metro.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental assessment of the multi-band access-metro continuum is performed by deploying various connectivity services.

Fig. 10 reports the workflow implemented among the several control plane components for performing: (1) the topology discovery and, (2) the establishment of a cross-domain IP adjacency. During the discovery phase, the IPoWDM orchestrator

Fig. 11. Filed-trial topology as retrieved by the Multi-domain IPoWDM Network Orchestrator.

concurrently queries both the intra-domain orchestrators and the IP SDN controller to collect IP and optical topology data. This request is relayed by the intra-domain orchestrators to their respective Optical SDN controllers. The retrieved topology is illustrated in Fig. 11 In the subsequent IP adjacency provisioning across domains: (i) a user initiates a request for an IP adjacency; (ii) the IPoWDM orchestrator supplies the PCE with a unified, domain-agnostic optical topology of both domains and solicits path computation, including spectrum and power assignments. For multi-domain paths, (iii-a) the IPoWDM initiates provisioning of intra-domain OLS paths in parallel, translating intents into Optical SDN controller instructions. Simultaneously, (iii-b) it manages IP/BGP configurations and adjusts pluggable module parameters — such as frequency and transmission power — through the SDN controller. This approach aligns with the *Single SBI management* scheme advocated by the TIP MANTRA working group [17].

The provisioning workflow illustrated Fig. 10 is applied to six 100G channels established between C-Tpx transponders located at Aggregation and Metro nodes (Fig. 12a). Additionally, two 400ZR channels are successfully deployed across IPoWDM nodes, traversing the aggregation-metro boundary transparently (Fig. 12b). Lastly, O-band channels connecting Access and Hub nodes are configured (Fig. 12c and Fig. 12d). Fig. 12e and Fig. 12f respectively report the topology of the access segment as retrieved by the FlexOpt controller (implementing the Intra-domain Network Orchestrator) and by the ONOS controller (implementing the Optical SDN Controller). Finally, a use case of the use of telemetry for degradation detection using optical constellations telemetry was demonstrated. Specifically, two degradation steps were manually produced to the optical signal, which made that the features of extracted change with the time as shown in Fig. 12g. The collected constellations together with the expected 95% confidence estimated gaussian function from four selected constellation points is also represented with an ellipse are shown in Fig. 12h. The dispersion of the constellation points in the received signal as compared to the expected estimated gaussian functions enable degradation detection.

As reported in the log in Fig. 13, within each domain, the setup time for the optical paths remains below 1 second. The PCE latency is below 0.1s, including execution of the PLI-aware RSA algorithm to determine the optimal path, spectral allocation, and launch power levels. The log also highlights that the orchestration process leverages parallel provisioning across the involved domains, allowing optical and IP configuration in

Fig. 12. Experimental results: optical spectra (a-d), topology views (e, f), monitoring data on 400ZR (g, h).

Fig. 13. Detail of the Multi-domain IPoWDM Network Orchestrator logs, also including the path validation to the PCE.

Fig. 15. SOA-based switch performance: gain as a function of the drive current.

Fig. 14. Wireshark capture on the SDN Optical controller of the access segment.

each segment to proceed concurrently. As a result, the configuration of IP/BGP sessions and pluggable modules takes less than 4 seconds in total. Most importantly, the entire end-to-end service provisioning, from request reception to adjacency establishment, is completed in approx. 10 milliseconds of orchestrator processing time.

Fig. 14 reports the capture of packets sent and received by the ONOS instance implementing the SDN Optical Controller of the access of the access segment. The first row in the capture shows the moment in which the controller receives the HTTP POST sent by the Intra-domain Network Orchestrator, the subsequent lines report the TCP packets that transported the NETCONF messages required to configure the ROADMs involved in the activation of the lightpath.

From a data plane standpoint, the O-band OADM introduces 11 dB of insertion loss, which includes the multiband mux/demux components. Fiber loss is measured at 4 dB over 10 km between Aggregation nodes and 2 dB over 5 km from Access to Aggregation. The OADM input signal power is set at 0 dBm. During bypass, the SOA is active, offering 17 dB gain to offset fiber and OADM losses. In drop mode, the SOA is

Fig. 16. SOA-based switch performance: Noise figure as a function of the drive current.

disabled (no bias current), effectively blocking the channel. An ON/OFF isolation ratio of 60 dB ensures minimal crosstalk and safe wavelength reuse. The received signal power at the drop port is measured at -15 dBm/ch, supporting error-free Ethernet frame reception.

The 400ZR C-band transceivers achieve a pre-FEC BER of approximately $3.6E-5$. Ethernet 25G O-band services at cell sites were error free (overall latency of 60 and 114 us was measured in Aggr1 and Aggr.2 nodes respectively, in compliance with fronthaul requirements). As shown in Fig. 15 and 16, the O-band SOA demonstrates high amplification for low input powers, achieving a maximum gain of 22 dB at 300 mA for an input power of -28 dBm. However, at higher input powers, the SOA enters saturation, with a 10 dBm input yielding only 0 dB gain (Fig. 15). The noise figure improves as the drive current increases, decreasing from approximately 19 dB at 50 mA to 10.5 dB at 300 mA for low input powers (Fig. 16). However, at an input power of 10 dBm, the noise figure remains high at around 15 dB even at 300 mA, indicating degraded noise performance. These performance characteristics highlight the critical role of the Orchestrator in optimizing SOA operation to ensure link quality. The Orchestrator must regulate the SOA not only to maintain the link power budget but also to consider the OSNR margin and the nonlinear effects of the SOA.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive field trial of a disaggregated IPoWDM network has been successfully demonstrated, enabling transparent interconnection across access, horseshoe aggregation, and metro segments while operating over both C and O-bands. The experimental validation incorporates SOA-based switching in the O-band, supporting dynamic and loss-compensated switching functionalities. By extending the optical continuum from the antenna sites through the access domain to the aggregation hubs, and seamlessly bridging into the C-band metro-core without intermediate opto-electronic conversion, the architecture achieves end-to-end transparency across heterogeneous domains.

The network operation was managed by an innovative hierarchical SDN-based control plane, capable of computing and enforcing transparent paths spanning multiple administrative domains, spectral bands, and network layers. The control plane

integrated multi-domain orchestration capabilities, leveraging standardized protocols and modeling languages to unify management across IP and optical layers. This approach enabled dynamic path provisioning while maintaining interoperability with disaggregated, multi-vendor components.

The experimental results validated both the data plane feasibility and the control plane scalability, confirming the ability to achieve transparent, multi-band service continuity without always incurring the cost and power consumption penalties of electronic regeneration.

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